

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HAMANDAWANA****FIRST NAME: YGAINNIA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MSWord Office 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The structure of an academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
2. Rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
3. American versus British English variants (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

I have always prided myself on a good command of English. This confidence has been the cumulative result of English being one of the official languages in my country (Zimbabwe) and simultaneously sharpened owing to the demands of my professional work. If ACA-401/ACA-401D were an optional course of study, I would have made a big mistake and chosen not to take it up.

Notwithstanding, I was surprised as I reviewed ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack and tutorial video. Admittedly, some of the course content refreshed my knowledge. Still, a large part of it was new altogether, highlighting the significance of this course in preparing other students and me for the journey ahead. I realized I had taken many things for granted in academic essay writing, which can negatively impact good research without careful consideration. In this response paper, I will discuss these, focusing on five concepts: the structure of an academic essay, rules of thumb for writing a paper, American and British English variants, plagiarism, and style guides.

2) THE STRUCTURE OF AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack reminded me that formulating a logical and coherent essay requires thinking that questions why, and develops an argument supported by evidence and expanding ideas. Writing an essay requires a reasonable time investment as the process is iterative, involving editing and redrafting cycles. Of importance as well is that an essay should follow a defined structure to present arguments logically and coherently, ensuring a smooth flow from sentence to sentence and paragraph to paragraph. (Victoria University 2015) recommends an essay structure that includes an introduction, body, and conclusion. EUCLID (2021,10) suggests the same structure for an essay.

The introduction is the opening paragraph of the essay. It starts with a broad statement about the topic, providing a general understanding. This comprehensive statement is followed by a thesis statement demonstrating the main argument. The introduction should be short and direct, as expounding on the argument is done in the essay's body.

The essay's body consists of paragraphs, each supporting the thesis statement and focusing on one main point. Furthermore, each paragraph should have a topic sentence that tells the reader what to expect in the rest of the paragraph, and supporting sentences to expound the topic sentence (Edith Cowan University 2015). A writer should provide evidence in developing the argument, with his or her voice visible, as demonstrated by analyzing and interpreting such evidence. Analyzing and interpreting the evidence allows the writer to exhibit knowledge and mastery. Lastly, the paragraph's conclusion should be based on the evidence discussed (EUCLID 2021, 11).

In the last section of the essay, the conclusion, the writer restates his or her thesis concerning the topic. The writer further summarizes the main points provided to support the thesis statement. Lastly, the writer can also suggest areas for supplementary investigation.

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

I firmly believe jargon or complicated phrasing is imperative in Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) level essay writing. Moreso, it was inculcated in me from primary education that writing in the first-person singular is inappropriate for essays. As I reviewed the course pack for ACA-401/ACA-401D, I learned that these beliefs do not conform with some basic rules for essay writing. According to EUCLID (2021, 13), an essay should be written clearly and use the first person singular to personalize it. Personalizing an essay also guards against using sweeping or general statements and conclusions, as these insinuate that the writer has no solid evidence on the subject matter.

Additional rules for essay writing include stating the thesis right at the beginning, staying focused and describing the specific aspects of the theory before moving to the

evaluation, and writing in an exciting manner to retain the reader's attention (EUCLID 2021, 13).

The rule I found most interesting is the need to consider the views I discuss when writing an essay critically. This rule calls for reflection and arguing against my arguments and conclusions to refine evidence to substantiate these further. In so doing, I can contemplate questions, counterarguments, and possible responses from the philosopher I will criticize. These processes culminate in the bolstering of evidence in the essay to make it credible.

In providing evidence to support my assertions, a point of emphasis throughout the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack is to ensure that all sources are cited. Citing all sources of information is a safeguard against plagiarism.

4) PLAGIARISM

“Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34). In other words, plagiarism is a form of theft where one presents other people’s ideas as own without any acknowledgment of the source. Plagiarism stems from the belief that copying is a minor offense (Bos 2020, 71).

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack re-emphasized plagiarism as an academic offense with profound implications. It is, therefore, my responsibility to give credit where it is due and cite all sources of information that do not represent any original ideas. Acknowledging sources of information is also ethical. Citations can assume one of two forms: in-text and bibliography at the end of the essay. The use of direct quotations or paraphrases characterizes an in-text citation. For direct quotations, the author of the passage and the page where the information came from should be indicated (EUCLID 2021, 35).

Paraphrasing is governed by guidelines, and failure of which to adhere results in plagiarism. These guidelines include using my own words, a different writing style, and accurately representing the original passage in the paraphrase. Beyond the stated guidelines, paraphrasing requires that the source of information be cited, which I was unaware of before reviewing the course pack. Consequently, I realize I have unknowingly plagiarized a few times due to failing to cite the source after paraphrasing.

Another form of plagiarism that I want to add involves the translation of passages or sentences published initially in one language, such as English, into another, in whole or in part. The translation can be word for word, but sometimes a writer may cut corners and substitute some words resulting in the loss of the original and intended meaning.

5) STYLE GUIDES

A style guide provides rules for writing and designing a document (Shigwan 2016, 163). These rules span different aspects like numbering and indentation, sentence lengths, font, and use of abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 41-42).

I have established that some style guides are discipline-specific, and examples of these include American Medical Association (AMA) for medicine and biology, American Psychological Association (APA) for social sciences, Associated Press Stylebook (AP) for journalism, and Scientific Style and Format (SSF) for sciences, (Enago Academy n.d.). However, the Chicago Style (Turabian), unlike the style guides mentioned above, can be used for research and academic work regardless of discipline. This style is also the recommended style guide by EUCLID.

I have gained practical knowledge on the importance and use of a style guide, which I will apply in my studies and professional work. Part of my professional work responsibilities include leading and coordinating country and regional-level reporting, and I have faced numerous challenges given that there is no style guide in place. Often, I have had to re-write sections allocated to and authored by other colleagues due to glaring inconsistencies. Broadly, such discrepancies have stemmed from different voice preferences (active versus passive) and content length produced, whereas others have authored multiple pages of solid paragraphs. In contrast, others have only half a page of bullet points and numbering overall.

6) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

American and British English are variants of World English, with American English being more dominant than British. Notwithstanding, these two have more similarities than differences (EUCLID 2021, 25). Spellings of some of the words may be similar, but with different pronunciations, and in the same vein, the spellings may differ but have identical pronunciations. The American variant uses singular nouns, whereas the British variant uses collective nouns. Further differences include using singular adjectives in the American variant compared to pluralized adjectives in the British variant.

I have learned that one language variant should be used consistently throughout an essay. Beforehand, a writer must decide which variant to use so that the two are not interchangeable. The main difficulty I have faced in preparing documents in my personal and professional work is not being able to tell the two apart, mainly where the difference will be in spelling and not meaning. I have, therefore, often used a mix of British and American English in one document due to a lack of knowledge on the need for consistency. I will adhere to this learned principle.

7) CONCLUSION

The crux of academic essay writing is communicating a logical and coherent argument. The student must understand guidelines for essay writing which include acknowledging the source of information used in arguments, using the recommended structure, using an appropriate style guide, using English variant of choice consistently between American and British, and correctly using punctuations. Essay writing goes beyond merely presenting evidence and citing the source, but analyzing and interpreting the evidence to make the writer's voice visible, demonstrating critical thinking.

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